

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE FINANCING MECHANISM OF AGROCLUSTERS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: this article highlights the potential of agroclusters in agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan, its global experience and the importance of agroclusters in the development of the country's economy. In the article, the global experience of agroclusters, their role in ensuring food security in the country is studied in detail. Clustering introduces a new system of financing to agriculture. The role of the state in financing agriculture is reduced. The cluster is fully self-investing and self-financing

Key words: agrocluster, financing, investment, agriculture, food security, gross domestic product, gross national product, institutional changes, credit, subsidy, subsidy.

Introduction: Institutional changes in the country help economic growth. This practice is known from the development history of all developed countries. Economic development of the country will be accelerated through clustering of economic sectors. Taking this into account, the Republic of Uzbekistan switched to the clustering system in the agricultural sector. Clustering effectively affects the entire activity of the network and fundamentally changes the process of agricultural financing. We can solve the above tasks by introducing agroclusters and cooperation in agriculture. Clusters can be formed and efficiently organized not only in agriculture, but in all sectors of the economy.

All countries are currently trying to ensure food safety. This requires radical reform of agriculture, digitization and efficient use of agricultural resources. It is of urgent importance to stop subsidizing agriculture and turn this sector into a profitable one. Our country, as a part of the world community, is trying to introduce major reforms in agriculture. Uzbekistan is a country with rich agricultural infrastructure. Effective use of resources will lead to full satisfaction of growing national needs and further increase of export opportunities.

Agroclusters in the agricultural network can be a driver of effective growth of the country's economy. Agroclusters not only provide the domestic market with a variety of goods, but also provide an impetus to improve the lifestyle of rural residents. The infrastructure of the regions will change radically. It serves to ensure food safety in our country.

Between 1860 and 1910, new clusters of technological innovation emerged, resulting in the emergence of the so-called heavy and chemical industries: the production of electrical appliances, internal combustion engines, synthetic dyes, artificial fertilizers, and other products.

In the formation and development of agroclusters, their financing forms and directions are also important. There are currently many problems in this direction.

The main problem is the current old financing procedure, said the President.

- It absolutely does not meet the requirements for the development of the industry. Cotton-textile clusters are asking for extension of credit terms and increase in amount. This old system is now completely changed.

If we analyze the economic situation of the countries of the world, at present, clusters cover about 17% of the economic activity as an effective growth driver of the economy of the countries of the world. For example, in the USA there are 380 clusters and they account for about 60% of GDP. 43% of those employed in Italian industry work in 206 clusters, and the share of these clusters in the country's exports is 30%.

In China, more than 60 special clusters unite about 30,000 enterprises and employ 3.5 million people. These enterprises produce products worth 200 billion dollars a year.

In 2018-2022, the volume of investments directed to clusters increased 5.2 times, and the number of people employed in the system increased 2.5 times.

The share of clusters in the total export of industrial products was 5 percent in 2019, and in 2022 it reached 11.4 percent.

In the period from 2018 to 2022, the production productivity in the cluster system increased 12.9 times, the investment profitability (APP) coefficient increased from 1 to 1.4. This shows that clustering projects are very effective.

According to the experience of the developed countries of the world, Clustering leads to an increase in productivity and efficiency indicators in the economy.

Clustering in industrial sectors allows the formation of a complete production system from raw materials to finished products, as well as the integration of such areas as science, trade, and logistics into this system.

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